

In vivo R2* and Quantitative Susceptibility Mapping on the 11.7T whole-body Iseult MRI System using Universal Pulses Transmission and Virtual Coil Reconstruction

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SYNOPSIS

This work presents the first in vivo R2* and susceptibility maps obtained on the 11.7T whole body Iseult system, using Universal Pulses for transmission and a virtual coil approach for coil combination.

INTRO

QSM at ultra-high field presents strong benefits due to an enhancement of the susceptibility effect¹. However, B0 and B1 field inhomogeneity make full exploitation difficult. Here we present the first in vivo R2* and magnetic susceptibility (QSM) maps obtained on a cohort of healthy subjects (PREMS cohort) acquired with the whole-body 11.7T Iseult magnet using universal pulses² (UP) and a virtual coil approach³ for coil combination. Normative values of R2* and susceptibility (QSM) were derived in the basal ganglia using a combined manual and deep learning approach for tissue segmentation.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The in vivo protocol was approved by the national ethics committee and regulatory authorities (ANSM). Images were acquired in parallel transmission (pTx) mode using the UP for flip angle homogenization on nine healthy volunteers (mean age was 22.3 +/- 6.5 years old, 7 women /2 men) with no known neurological diseases. Data were acquired using the 11.7T Magnetom Iseult MRI with Siemens Healthineers VE12U software. A custom 8/32-channel pTx head coil was used for signal emission and reception⁴. Images were acquired using a whole-brain 3D Multi Echo Gradient Echo sequence with an isotropic resolution of 0.8 mm. Parameters were: FOV= 220x220x179 mm³, matrix size= 276x276x224, TR = 25 ms, TEs ranging from 3.50 to 17.36 ms with a Δ TE of 4.62 ms (4 echoes acquired), readout bandwidth = 430 Hz/pix. Flip angle was 10° and only one average was acquired. A 2x2 GRAPPA scheme and elliptical sampling were used to speed up the acquisition, leading to a scan time of 5 minutes 14 s. Raw data was saved for further processing. Magnitude and Phase images were generated offline, and coil combination was performed using a Virtual Coil approach using Matlab. Images of multiple echoes were combined using a root mean square along time dimension, thus providing both high SNR and T2*-contrasted images. Brain mask was obtained using “bet” (FSL). Transversal relaxation rate (R2*) was evaluated using a nonlinear fitting method in Matlab. Quantitative Susceptibility Mapping (QSM) images were reconstructed using several functions from the MEDI Toolbox^{5,6} for both background field removal and dipole inversion, using respectively Laplacian Boundary Value (LBV) and a GPU modified L1-MEDI function. Three templates of

Magnitude, R2* and QSM were generated using Ants multivariate⁷. Regions of Interest (ROIs) were defined on the magnitude template using a deep learning model trained on synthetic data⁸. ROIs were then manually edited using Slicer. Finally, ROI were back-projected to the subject space to provide subject-specific ROIs.

RESULTS

Figure 1 presents the images obtained in one of the volunteers using the proposed framework for anatomical T2*w, fitted phase image, miP-SWI, R2* and quantitative susceptibility maps. Virtual coil combination provided naturally unbiased and usable magnitude images (no normalization used). Moreover, no clear evidence of abnormal signal inhomogeneity due to bad RF shimming or coil combination were identified on these images. Figure 2 presents the defined ROIs overprinted on the magnitude template, as well as the R2* and QSM templates. R2* and susceptibility values are reported in Table 1 for Caudate Nuclei, Putamen, Globus Pallidus, Red Nuclei and Substantia Nigra. Interestingly, several phase singularities can be detected in phase images before coil combination but did not interfere on the final computed susceptibility maps (not shown).

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

We report in this work the first R2* and susceptibility maps obtained at 11.7T on healthy subjects at 800 μm isotropic spatial resolution obtained in roughly 5 minutes. Universal pulses and virtual coil combination allowed to provide *in vivo* R2* and susceptibility maps without severe RF field inhomogeneity artefacts. We now intend to compare the values obtained in the basal ganglia at 11.7T to those obtained at 3 and 7T using an age-matched cohort. We will also refine the MR acquisition protocol at 11.7T to enhance the image resolution to detect small details and that might not be visible at conventional field strength *in vivo*.

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	Caudate	Putamen	Globus Pallidus	Red Nuclei	Substantia Nigra
T2* [ms]	25.0 +/- 2.0	21.9 +/- 2.2	13.4 +/- 0.6	16.4 +/- 1.8	15.9 +/- 1.1
R2* [Hz]	40.0 +/- 3.3	45.6 +/- 5.0	74.7 +/- 5.0	61.1 +/- 7.2	62.9 +/- 4.4
QSM [ppb]	37.5 +/- 14.1	13.5 +/- 16.9	89.2 +/- 13.3	62.7 +/- 20.4	66.0 +/- 21.1

Table 1: ROI mean and standard deviation values of T2* [ms], R2* [Hz] and susceptibility [ppb] in Caudate, Putamen, Globus Pallidus, Red Nuclei and Substantia Nigra.

Figure 1: Coronal (Top row) and Axial (Bottom row) views of one volunteer for A) T2*-weighted image, B) Fitted phase over the 4 echoes, C) miP-SWI, D) R2* map (scaling 0:100 Hz) and E) Susceptibility (QSM) map (scaling -200:200 ppb).

Figure 2: Coronal (Top row) and Axial (Bottom row) views of the obtained templates for A) T2*-weighted image and obtained ROIs, B) R2* map and C) Susceptibility (QSM) map. Color for ROIs are: Green : Putamen, Blue: Globus Pallidus, Yellow: Caudate, Red: Red Nuclei and Purple: Substantia Nigra.

